

Uses of non-pressure membranes for microalgae biomass harvesting

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Abstract

Harvesting of microalgae biomass is a major challenge in the development of industrial processes related to the management of this type of microorganism. Thus, microalgae are small cells (<10 µm) produced in diluted cultures (<3 g/L) in large volumes of water (>1000 m³/reactor), thus the separation of biomass from the culture broth represents up to 30% of operating costs (Acien et al., 2017). The conventional technology for microalgae harvesting includes the direct centrifugation of the culture or a combination of pre-concentration + dewatering using sedimentation or dissolved air flotation before centrifugation. However, none of these technologies allows for the complete removal of the microalgae cells from the culture broth, with a percentage of microalgae cells remaining which is difficult for the safe disposal of this water or its reuse. The recent development of non-pressure membranes used for membrane bioreactors allows the development of more sustainable processes for the harvesting of microalgae biomass in large-scale processes.

In the present study, the operation of non-pressure membranes for the pre-concentration of microalgae cultures is studied. An experimental setup was designed for this purpose (Figure 1). The operation of the system was firstly optimized, thus the filtration time and frequency of back-wash to achieve stable operation of the membrane was determined. Next, the influence of operational conditions (pressure, biomass concentration) on the performance of the system (flow, specific filtration capacity) was evaluated. Based on these results a model capable of predicting the performance of the process is developed, being a useful tool for the scale-up of these technologies.

Figure 1.- Image of harvesting system using non-pressure membranes used during the research

References

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